

ISic0274

Epitaph for Aulus Magullius

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Already lost by the time of Gualtherus

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. A(ulo) · Magullio
2. A(uli) · I(liberto) · Euhodo
3. Magullia · Tyche
4. patrono · et · co
5. niugiiugi · monumen
6. tum · fecit
7. o(ptime) · d(e) · s(e) · m(erito)

Apparatus

Text of Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To Aulus Magullius Euhodus, freedman of Aulus. Magullia Tyche erected this monument for her patron and spouse who has behaved excellently with her.

Translation (it)

Ad Aulo Magullio Euhodus, liberto di Aulo. Magullia Tyche ha eretto questo

monumento per il suo patrono e consorte che è stato meritevole verso di lei.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284760

EDR 033600

EDCS 21900304

PHI 313694

Bibliography

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